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Abstract

This document describes the evaluation process and the evaluation results of the procuRE Call-off for Phase III. Two suppliers were selected to participate in Phase III.

Revision History

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Statement of originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

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ACRONYMS

Acronym	Meaning
BMS	Building Management System
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning
IPR	Intellectual Property Right
PCP	Pre-commercial Procurement
PV	Photovoltaics
RfT	Request for Tenders

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable reports on the conditions and outcome of the evaluation of the call-off for Phase III. A detailed overview of the evaluation methodology is presented in D3.1.

The work of the three suppliers during Phase II constituted the baseline for this iteration of the call-off. The procurers evaluated the bids submitted for Phase III, closed on April 11th 2023, with all three supplier consortia submitting bids for the next and final phase of the PCP.

An evaluation committee evaluated the bids submitted using the award criteria set out in the RfT. All three bids achieved the minimum criteria and were deemed eligible from the side of the buyers group. The two highest ranked bids in terms of price and quality were selected and awarded the contract. However, due to repeated delays and difficulties in signing the specific contract with one of the originally selected suppliers, the Buyers Group had to review the decision and award the contract to the third-ranking tenderer.

The evaluation outcome was finally concluded on July 30th 2023, with the reviewed decision communicated to the final tenderer and the contracts were sent for signature and signed by the suppliers.

Phase III of the project started on July 31st 2023 and is intended to last 15 months.

1 The evaluation process

1.1 Role of the Evaluation Committee and the Expert Board

As defined in the Request for Tenders, the evaluation of the tenders is performed by an Evaluation Committee constituted by the project consortium member which was assisted by an Expert Board.

The procuRE Evaluation Committee

The Evaluation Committee remained unchanged since the evaluation of tenders.

The Evaluation Committee was responsible for performing the evaluation of all tenders following the procedures and according to the criteria specified in the Request for Tenders. The lead procurer representative, Niko Natek at KSENA, chaired it.

Each procurer nominated at least two experts to represent them in evaluating procurement, technical, and business issues. A total of 20 Evaluation Committee Members were nominated and accepted:

Table 1. Members of the Evaluation Committee

Procurer	Name of Evaluation Committee
KSENA	Niko Natek
	Nejc Jurko
	Boštjan Krajnc
AMB	Marta Pascual
	Sergi Pérez
	Gil Lladó
NUREMBERG	Alexander Nordhus
	Peter Pfeifer
	Mathias Klaussner
	Thomas Schad
PORTO	João Encarnação
	Carlos Inácio
IMM	Hasan Mancak
	Mehmet Keskin
	Yıldız Münevver Rüzgaroğlu
	Sefer Meşe
EILAT	Avi Naim
	Asaf Admon
	Elad Topel
	Dudu Zatch

The procuRE Expert Board

The procuRE Expert Board has already consulted the procuRE partners in the first two phases of the project as well as before launching the call for tender by informing the consortium on technical requirements and offering their insights on the initial offers.

The Board consists of:

- Daniel Mugnier
- Diego Bertolina
- Jorge Rodrigues de Almeida
- Wim van Helden.

Ensuring no conflicts of interest

Upon closing the call for tender and drawing up the list of tenderers, the Evaluation Committee and the Expert Board members were required to sign a declaration of absence of conflict of interest. The declaration defines key commitment points.

The declarations can be found in D3.1 (Annex 2).

Ensuring the protection of confidential information

The Evaluation Committee and the Expert Board members are also required to protect confidential data during the PCP process. The protection of confidentiality clauses is part of the declaration of absence of conflict and can be found in D3.1 (Annex 2).

1.2 Approval of Phase II results

The evaluation process also considered the approval of the deliverables linked to Phase II, as well as the contractors’ offers for Phase III.

Deliverables from all suppliers were considered successful; therefore, their offers were eligible for Phase III. The following table presents the summary of these deliverables.

Table 2. Summary of milestones and deliverables in phase II

Milestones	By when?	How?	Output & results
M2.1 Prototype system v1 ready	5 months before end of phase (see Section 2.6)	Presentation of prototypes of key system components	D2.4a/b
M2.2 Prototype system v2 ready	1 month before end of phase (see Section 2.6)	Presentation of all functional prototypes, demonstrating component behaviour and system-wide interaction	D2.5a/b
M2.3 All detailed designs of Renovation Packages and revised Renovation Approach	One month before end of phase (see Section 2.6)	Reports	D2.1, D2.2, Offer

Deliverables	By when?	How?	Output & results
D2.1 Renovation Approach	4 months before end of phase (see Section 2.6)	Sent by email to the Lead Procurer	Improved and extended version of D1.1.
	1 month before end of phase (see Section 2.6)	This deliverable is rated along with the offer O2 with the corresponding award criteria.	
D2.2 Renovation Packages	6 Renovation Packages one each for all sites 4 months before end of phase (see Section 2.6)	Sent by email to the Lead Procurer and relevant procurer.	Improved and extended version of D1.2.
	6 Renovation Packages, one each for all sites 1 month before end of phase (see Section 2.6)	This deliverable is rated as part of award criteria T2, CF1 and T3.	

One **updated, extended and detailed Renovation Package** per demonstration site is expected, each Package is to contain at least the following content:

- An Executive Summary including explanatory graphics of no more than two pages understandable by non-experts.*
- **Detailed Design** (plans and schematics) with high detail of all technical systems (mechanical, electric, monitoring and control, architectural and structural, if subject of the Renovation Package)*
- The list and description of materials and components used for the retrofit, the guarantees and certifications on the materials and related aftersales services intended to be provided. Solutions must be included for heating & cooling which ensures hygrothermal comfort and air quality (Indoor Environment Quality - IEQ) inside the structures*
- The detailed description of the system adopted for metering, measurement and control of energy flows and the identification of faults inside the buildings, allowing for monitoring and verification of performance, as well as the easy access for operators *
- Final, detailed installation work plan, including procedures for dealing with old materials, transportation flows, stocking on site, installation of new systems and realistic Gantt charts of the activities under the assumption of retrofitting three buildings in parallel.
- Final ordinary and extraordinary maintenance plans, including i) assignment of responsibilities and description of intervention flows, ii) intervention times after notification of failures, iii) maintenance status and useful life of the materials installed at the end of the (service) contract.
- Detailed assessment of the Renovation Package energy, environmental and IEQ performance, based at least on the KPIs reported in the Technical Tender Application Template and calculated at least on a daily basis (TD6)*
- Final detailed economic plan including the structure of contracts for energy and system-relevant facility management services, clarity on ownerships and a clear and concise calculation of all costs for procurers at least on a yearly basis (e.g. annual fees, design, investment, operation and maintenance costs), including the use of incentives, contracting schemes and financing models as well as an uncomplicated rule set for discretions from performance benchmark / KPIs induced by either party**
- Training and education measures which will be implemented on site (Description of necessary measures to achieve 100% RES operation and how measures should best be deployed based on use and users of the building).***
- Annex with results from building audit, surveys, site visit.

* Evaluated as part of award sub-criterion T2; ** Evaluated as part of CF1; *** Evaluated as part of T3

D2.3 Report on Co-Design Procedure with procurers	6 procures by 1 months before end of phase. (see Section 2.6)	Sent by email to the Lead Procurer and relevant procurer.	Documentation or exports generated by Co-Design procedure. The progress is expected to influence D2.2. Lessons learnt are expected to be incorporated in D2.1.
D2.4a Presentation of initial prototypes of key systems	5 months before end of phase (see Section 2.6). Procurers welcome an earlier presentation potentially enabling earlier invoicing (see Section 5.5).	Online presentation to each procurer on a widely available web platform. On-site demonstration to EURAC where required. Also sent by email to the Lead Procurer	Presentation of initial prototypes, first training materials and test bench.

The D2.4a presentation and/or report includes:

- Description of all IT-systems, services and components and systems to be tested
- Description of where the above-listed items are tested and the test protocol – Smaller devices can be sent to technical partner EURAC, for larger installations EURAC staff would visit contractor labs for v1
- The status of IT-systems and materials may not be complete or only partially functional.
- With regard to user-facing IT-systems, permissions for remote online testing by procurers and selected users (operators and occupants) is provided in English language- procurers will recruit users for testing
- With regard to training and learning tools, provision of or access to training and learning tools (online and offline) provided in English language – procurers will recruit users for testing

D2.4b Protocol of testing v1	4 months before end of phase (see Section 2.6)	Sent by email to the Lead Procurer	Protocol of testing v1: test bench and test procedure, verifiable data sheets etc. Lessons learnt, improvements and critical data etc. are expected to be incorporated in D2.1 and calculations in D2.2 updated accordingly.
D2.5a Presentation of functional prototypes, demonstrating component behaviour and system-wide interaction	2 months before end of phase (see Section 2.6)	On-site presentation to EURAC and procurers Also sent by email to the Lead Procurer	Presentation of functional prototypes and training material.

The D2.5a presentation and/or report includes:

- Description of all IT-systems, services and components and systems to be tested
- Description on where above listed items are tested and the test protocol – Smaller devices can be sent to technical partner EURAC, for larger installations EURAC staff would visit contractor labs for v2
- The status of IT-systems and materials is to be **complete and fully functional**.
- With regard to user-facing IT-systems, permissions for remote online testing by procurers and selected users (operators and occupants) is provided in **all procurer languages** - procurers will recruit users for testing
- With regard to training and learning tools, provision of or access to training and learning tools (online and offline) provided in **all procurer languages** – procurers will recruit users for testing

D2.5b Protocol of testing v2	1 month before end of phase (see Section 2.6)	Sent by email to the Lead Procurer	Protocol of testing v2, verifiable data sheets etc. Lessons learnt, improvements and critical data etc. are expected to be incorporated in D2.1 and calculations in D2.2 updated accordingly.
D2.6 GDPR compliance report	End of phase	Sent by email to the Lead Procurer	Presentation of conformance of the solutions with GDPR
D2.7a Project abstract	Start of Phase (see Section 2.6)	In the format required by the EU for publication Sent by email to the Lead Procurer	Update of D1.4a (template will be provided)
D2.7b End of phase report	End of phase (see Section 2.6)	Sent by email to the Lead Procurer	Written report See D1.4 for detail. (template will be provided)

Payments based on satisfactory completion of milestones and deliverables of the phase

Payments corresponding to each PCP phase **are subject to the *satisfactory completion*** of the deliverables and milestones for that phase. This will be assessed by the Evaluation Committee composed of representatives of the Buyers Group, and will consider the following requirements:

- if the work corresponding to that milestone/deliverable has been carried out
- if a reasonable minimum quality (see below) has been delivered
- if the reports have been submitted on time
- if the monies have been allocated to the planned objectives
- if the monies have been allocated and the work has been carried out according to the on/off criteria (place of performance, public funding and R&D definition criteria), and
- if the work has been carried out in compliance with the provisions of the contract (including, in particular, verifying if the contractor has duly protected and managed IPRs generated in the respective phase).

‘Reasonable minimum quality’ of a report means that:

- the report can be read by somebody who is familiar with the topic, but not an expert
- the report gives insight into the tasks performed and the results
- the report uses any reasonable template or form provided to the tenderer.

‘Reasonable minimum quality’ of a demonstration (for Phase III) means:

- the demonstration can be understood by somebody who is familiar with the topic, but not an expert (for instance, somebody with operational but not technical knowledge)
- the demonstration shows how the innovation works, how it can be used and, if applicable, how it is operated and maintained
- the demonstration is accessible to parties appointed by the procurers unless these are direct competitors of the contractor.

Satisfactory completion in each of the phases does not mean successful completion. A PCP could, for instance, be satisfactorily completed even if it concludes that the innovation is not feasible.

1.3 Payments for Phase II

Payments are made conditional on the acceptance of deliverables (shown in section 1.2) by the Buyers Group according to formerly defined technical and quality related criteria. All three contractors involved in Phase II submitted all requested deliverables, which were rated satisfactory by all procurers. Invoicing for both phases was completed.

Since the budget in Phase II was not fully used, it is expected that **€889,248** from the PCP budget of Phase II are transferred to Phase III. The large sum is result of the fact that only three suppliers entered the call-off for Phase II whilst the Tender has foreseen four suppliers.

In total **€1,609,161** from Phase I and II have been transferred to Phase III. These values do not include associated VAT costs for the provision of R&D services, which have amounted to €406,302 for both phases.

1.4 Invitation to tender

The procuRE project is constituted by six demonstration buildings which can only be served by one supplier at a time, i.e. only one Renovation Package based on the Supplier's Renovation Approach can be installed at any given building in its entirety to measure the performance of the Renovation Package and thereby learn about the validity and replicability of the Renovation Approach.

Hence, a Supplier chosen for Phase III will serve three demonstration buildings. The allocation is in the discretion of the Buyers Group (see RfT TD1 2.1.2).

The Suppliers were informed on multiple occasions (among others, original tender, bilateral monitoring February 09th 2023 and March 17th 2023) that the allocation will be decided after evaluation.

The Suppliers were informed during a joint meeting on March 17th 2023 (see Annex 1 PowerPoint Call-Off Invitation) that – for simplicity of the offers and evaluation – only two sets of offers will be requested not constituting the final decision and documented in the invitation letter (see Annex 2 Invitation Letter).

1.5 Opening of tenders

The Lead Procurer opened the Phase III tenders electronically **on April 12th, 2023**. Technical and administrative forms were shared beforehand with the Buyers Group and all partners for the evaluation process.

1.6 Evaluation process

For a detailed description of the process, please see the Tender Documents (D2.1), particularly the 'PCP Request for Tenders' (TD1).

Exclusion criteria

No changes to supplier consortia occurred.

Selection criteria

No changes to supplier consortia occurred.

Compliance criteria

No changes to supplier consortia occurred.

Award criteria

On/off award criteria

No changes to supplier consortia occurred.

Weighted award criteria

The weights and maximum points for each criterion for Phase III were as follows:

Table 3. Overview of weighted award criteria (Phase III)

Weighted award criteria	Maximum points	Threshold	Weight
Technical Criterion			50%
T1 – System Integration: Methodology and Process	30	15	
T2 – Degree of achievement of objectives in reference buildings	40	25	
T3 – Training & Education of professionals and users	20	15	
T4 – Innovativeness compared to market state-of-the-art	10	5	
Total for technical	100	60	
Commercial Feasibility Criterion			25%
CF1 – Investment, energy service contracting and financing models / Total cost of ownership	60	40	
CF2 – Commercialisation Plan	40	30	
Total for commercial feasibility	100	70	
Project Management Criterion			25%
PM1- Interface to procurers	25	15	
PM2 – Quality and completeness of the work-plan as well as detail of task and result descriptions	40	25	
PM3 – Feasibility of plan and resources to meet the objectives	35	20	
Total for project management	100	60	
Overall total score for tender	100	60	

The Evaluation Committee Members awarded points per criterion based on the following assessment table:

Table 4. procuRE assessment scheme

Assessment	Description	Score
Outstanding	The response exceeds the requirement providing significant added value to it, which is described very convincingly.	10
Excellent	The response fully meets the requirement, and the provided explanation is very convincing.	9
Very good	The response addresses the requirement very well, but a small number of inconsistencies, or minor shortcomings are present.	8
Good	The response addresses well the requirement in most respects and provides certain information which is relevant, but a small number of shortcomings are present.	7
Fairly good	The response meets the requirement in certain material respects and provides certain information, which is relevant, but which is lacking or inconsistent in material respects, or a number of shortcomings are present.	6
Fair	The response addresses multiple aspects of the requirement, but the provided explanation is not fully convincing, and a number of shortcomings are present.	5
Poor	The response broadly addresses the requirement, but there are multiple shortcomings.	4
Fairly poor	The response inadequately addresses the requirement, or it contains significant shortcomings.	3
Very poor	The response significantly fails to meet the requirements, or it contains serious shortcomings.	2
Extremely poor	Multiple important aspects of the requirement are missing.	1
Unacceptable	No response is provided, or none of the aspects of the requirement are met.	0

The Committee decided on the final award criteria's scoring by a simple majority vote in an online meeting. Points achieved for each criterion are calculated based on the score. The formula can be summarised as follows:

$$\text{Score (as defined in Table 4 * max points (see Table 3)) / Max score (10 from Table 4).}^1$$

Tenders were required to score above the thresholds given in the award criteria (see Table 3), for each threshold. For tenders that would not reach the minimum quality thresholds were to be rejected.

1.7 Evaluation time schedule

The evaluation was performed in the period between April 12th to July 30th 2023. The relatively long period was due to delays in the contract's signature (see Sections 2.1 and 2.2 for details) and subsequent revision of the decision. The original decision on the suppliers' selection was communicated to the tenderers on April 26th 2023, two weeks after opening of the offers. The final set of outcome letters was communicated on July 30th 2023 (see Annex 3: Notification emails).

1.8 Ranking of tenders

The price-quality ranking was created for all offers fulfilling the abovementioned process.

The contract was awarded to the most economically advantageous tender, i.e., the tender scoring above all thresholds mentioned earlier, which offers the best price-quality ratio determined in accordance with the formula below. The price applied consisted of the total offered price relating to the next specific contract (contract for each phase) in the PCP.

A weight of 80/20 is given to quality and price, respectively.

$$\text{Total Score}_{Tender i} = 80\% * \text{Quality}_{Tender i} + 20\% * \left(\frac{\text{lowest price of all tenders}}{\text{Price}_{Tender i}} * 100 \right)$$

1.9 Allocation of demonstration sites for Phase III

In line with TD1 and section "Invitation to tender" the sites further deliberated the most suitable allocation of Renovation Package to each Demonstration site to be allocated to the Suppliers. This exchange was conducted after determining the ranking and the best offers overall. The selection of sites required considerable willingness to reach a compromise on the side of procurers.

The Buyers Group has agreed to award the following sites. Set A (Velenje, Eilat and Vila Nova de Gaia) and Set B (Barcelona, Nuremberg and Istanbul). Upon the refusal of supplier Clarity (SENER) the procurers demonstrated further willingness to compromise and Gaia and Istanbul were exchanged between sets. The final allocation of demonstration sites is Velenje, Eilat and Istanbul in set A and Barcelona, Nuremberg and Vila Nova de Gaia for set B.

¹ For detail see Request for Tender TD1.

1.10 Award decision and notification

Tenderers were informed via E-Mail of the outcome of their proposal and, if applicable, the next steps (see *Annex 3: Notification emails*). The outcome letter contained the justification of the evaluation result (presented in *Annex 4: Outcome letters and Annex 5: Exchange with Clarity on concerning change of supplier*).

1.11 Delay of specific contract signature and revised timeline

The receipt of signed specific contracts was planned for 22nd of May 2023. However, the signatures were delayed upon extended discussions with the second ranked supplier which was ultimately replaced with the third ranked supplier proving unable to deliver the technical offer. For details see Section 2.2.

Table 5. procuRE tender evaluation timeline

Initial Date	Revised date	Activity
10.08.2022	-	Start of Phase II
17.03.2023	-	Call-off invitation and presentation including Specific Contract
11.04.2023	-	Submission of the offers for next phase
12.04.2023	-	Opening of Tenders for Phase III
30.04.2023	26.04.2023	Tenderers notified of the outcome of the evaluation with the original Sites allocated to each supplier
19.05.2023	19.05.2023	Evaluation comments were submitted to tenderers
22.05.2023	-	Original Deadline for receipt of signed contracts
-	30.07.2023	Revised notification to suppliers ranked 1st and 3rd and invitation to sign specific contracts.
-	08.08.2023	Date of signature by Lead Procurer
09.05.2023	31.07.2023	Start of Phase III

2 Evaluation results and abstracts of winning tenders

Three submissions were received for Phase III.

2.1 Award criteria – results

All tenders (three) were evaluated on the award criteria. All three met the minimum score thresholds and proceeded to be evaluated by applying the price-quality formula. The aggregated results are summarised in Table 6.

Initially, the first two ranked supplier consortia were invited. After multiple demands by the second-ranked consortium (Clarity, SENER) and extensive delays caused by uncertain prospects to start Phase III, the Buyers Group decided to award the contract to the third-ranked supplier (SEBR, Defcon8). For details, see Section 2.2.

Table 6. Evaluation results and ranking of tenders (order according to rank)

ID	Name of Tenderer	Tender	Rank	Price-Quality Score	Quality Score	Technical	Commercial Feasibility	Project Management
T005	R2M	PARadISE	1	79	74	74	77	73
T001	SENER	Clarity	2	78	73	74	74	73
T002	Defcon8	SEBR	3	72	65	64	70	61

2.2 Matters delaying Specific Contract signature

Three issues occurring in parallel delayed the final signature of specific contracts:

- Re-allocation of demonstration site in Eilat (Set A: PARadISE)
- Refinement of Specific Contract (all suppliers)
- Revision of the suppliers' selection (Set B: Clarity to SEBR)

All three issues could be resolved.

2.2.1 Re-allocation of demonstration site in Eilat (Set A: PARadISE)

This matter was resolved swiftly due to demonstrated flexibility of the PARadISE consortium and pro-activity of Eilat municipality. Overall, the change can be considered as a demonstration of the rapid adaptation of the Renovation Approach into a new Renovation Package.

On the 27th of April 2023 it became apparent that the envisaged demonstration site (i.e. the former Airport Terminal) in Eilat is no longer tenable. The Israeli federal ministry terminated the national funding foreseen to conduct exterior works on the Terminal which had been planned and were required to be able to implement procuRE Renovation Packages. The city was unable to find other funding. As a solution, three alternative buildings were identified as potential replacement of which ultimately the office of the municipality was chosen. PARadISE utilised the consortium meeting in Bonn to clarify key questions with Eilat and agreed to adopt the new building and re-develop an entirely new Renovation Packages applying the lessons learnt during Phase I and II.

It is stressed that Eilat’s team pro-activity to identify the possible solution as well as the PARadISE Team effort made the change in a fast pace and relatively simple. With the new building in mind PARadISE used the same tools developed within their Renovation Approach for the new building and delivered the financial feasibility and the initial technical planning for approval. Eilat and PARadISE meet every second week on Thursday for re-cap and updates. We expect to finalize the project on time and to be able to replicate its success to other buildings in the city.

2.2.2 Refinement of Specific Contract (all suppliers)

The supply shock in the construction sector changed the operation of the sector in comparison to the conditions foreseen when the Request for Tender was drafted. In particular, subcontractors and suppliers of equipment have substantially reduced the validity duration of their offers due to price volatility, the delivery periods have dramatically increased on multiple relevant systems and any binding offer must commit to substantial pre-payments before delivery.

In order to accommodate R&D partners the Buyers Group compromised that a larger share of the payment is conducted when the Renovation Packages are completed and the confirmed order submitted to local subcontractors. These are to provided as annexes to the invoices.

The final timetable in the Specific Contract reads:

Table 7. Timeframe for Specific contracts

Required deliverable/ milestone	Amount of payment	Date
D3.5a	10% (ten percent) of contractor’s Phase III price	10 days after start: 10.08.2023
Final Timeline		1 month after start: 31.08.2023
Confirmed Orders (as documentation as annex to Invoice)*	45% (forty-five percent) of Phase III price	As soon as available
M3.1**		4 months after the start of Phase: 30.11.2023
M3.2**, M3.3**, D3.2		5 months after the start of the Phase: 31.12.2023
D3.1, D3.3 (documentation of co-design during implementation), D3.4	10% (ten percent) of Phase III price	8 months after the start of Phase (31.03.2024)
D3.1, D3.2, D3.3 (including continuous commissioning), D3.4 - all final and complete		1 months before end of Phase (30.09.2024)
M3.4***		1 months before end of Phase (30.09.2024)
D3.5b, D3.6	35% (thirty-five percent) of Phase III price	End of Phase (30.10.2024)

* No site can be missing from the confirmed orders

** Each site should be delivered as soon as possible. Justified delays (e.g. delivery times, works) in any site need to be documented in writing should a delay occur. In all other instances, reporting remains limited to the deliverables, in particular D3.2 and D3.3.

*** If suppliers have taken all necessary measures to, plan order and install equipment as soon as possible and/or availability of installers have hindered an earlier installation, a shorter duration will be acceptable. The site must, in all instances, have been fully operational for a duration long enough to verify performance.

Approval of deliverables and invoicing shall proceed as specified in Section 5.5 of the Request for Tender.

2.2.3 Revision of the suppliers' selection (Set B: Clarity to SEBR)

After three months of being unable to sign the contract with Clarity, the Buyers Group decided to replace the Supplier with another tenderer. During the delay caused by Clarity, the second consortium – PARadISE – could not be contracted and could not trigger the subcontractors required to roll-out the project. Further, due to above-described developments in the construction sector, many offers have very limited time-constraints. As a result, the entire project accumulated significant delays in implementation and was jeopardised if further delays would be allowed. In particular, the entire summer holidays at all three schools were lost for effort on the buildings which cannot be safely conducted during school terms.

Table 8 records key events which led to the final decision of replacing the tenderer. A contract for Phase III activities was not signed.

The issue appears to have been resolved amenable with no communication exchanged since.

The following list includes many parallel developments with the cumulation of delay, non-performance and scope shifting leading to the decision of the consortium (see summarised reasoning submitted to Clarity in Annex 5: Exchange with Clarity on concerning change of supplier). The key events fall into the following categories constituting the cumulative reasons for the decision (in order of occurrence):

- Refusal to accept the demonstration site allocation (resolved through good-will compromise by both the Buyers Group and the second Supplier PARadISE)
- Re-organisation at SENER to be implemented on contracts
- Strategic changes announced by the new executive board at SENER in that the EPC-related business is to be discontinued and that the project is counter to the priorities of the business
- Inability to implement a one-stop-shop project delivery as contracted through RfT
- Delays and non-performance in Barcelona and increasingly apparent poor quality of Renovation Package preparation and local price sourcing in earlier Phases
- Delays and non-performance in Gaia and increasingly apparent poor quality of Renovation Package preparation and local price sourcing in earlier Phases
- Delays and non-performance in Nuremberg and increasingly apparent poor quality of Renovation Package preparation and local price sourcing in earlier Phases
- Uncovering the commercial unavailability of the Renovation Approach with formerly not provided information in that respire costs almost six-digit figures to be set up.
- Uncovering that Clarity has taken no measures to adopt and scale the Respira system for use in public buildings throughout Phase II (i.e. the installation of any given Respira system would cost around 70-90,000 Euro in any building independent of the size).

- Requests from Clarity to substantially modify the technical offer (i.e. removing Respira from the Renovation Package).
- Demands to cover costs or efforts considered to have been part of Phase I and II and/or as part of the overall service tendered in the procuRE RfT and Challenge Brief (e.g. efforts to ensure compliance with local planning and permits; local site management; local project management)

The following table documents some of the events and exchange between procuRE and Clarity.

Table 8. Selection of key events linked to revising the suppliers’ selection

Date (DD.MM.YYYY)	Sender	Description
11.04.2023	EMPIRICA	[Minutes from bi-weekly consortium meeting] Announcement of Consortium Meeting in Bonn for 23-24.05.2023. The aim was for procurers to discuss details for Phase III with suppliers.
26.04.2023	KSSENA (Lead Procurer)	Communication to originally selected consortia for Phase III (via email, Annex 3: Notification emails) with site allocation. It also announced the Consortium Meeting for Suppliers, asking them to ensure participation. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allocation to Clarity: Barcelona, Istanbul and Nuremberg. • Allocation to PARadISE: Eilat, Vila Nova de Gaia and Velenje
30.04.2023	EMPIRICA	Formal invitation (to suppliers), with preliminary agenda for the Consortium Meeting. The communication asked suppliers to prepare key topics (including arrangements with subcontractors) for Phase III to discuss with procurers.
03.05.2023	EMPIRICA	Documenting the announcement made by CLARITY concerning the updated strategic objectives of SENER and potential implications for the consortium during Phase III. Particularly SENER threatening to leave the project and the supplier’s difficulty in preparing the contract signature, establishing a delay for procuRE. Also, mitigation measures (by the Buyers Group) were mentioned to be further explored.
05.05.2023	EMPIRICA	E-mail after meeting with CLARITY (held on the same day: 05.05.2023), detailing on how to carry on with Phase III and preparation of contract. Initiation of the procedure among procurers and subsequently the other supplier to change sites. Statement by Clarity that sourcing of all costs would be possible within weeks after confirming sites.

Date (DD.MM.YYYY)	Sender	Description
05.05.2023	Nuremberg	Nuremberg's Point of Contact (POC) confirms CLARITY to support in the communication to suppliers and points out that still all project management must be carried out by CLARITY because it is part of the contract. No reply on that.
16.05.2023	EMPIRICA	<p>[Minutes from bi-weekly consortium meeting] Agreement and revised allocation of pilots. The following was agreed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allocation to Clarity: Barcelona, Vila Nova de Gaia and Nuremberg. • Allocation to PARadISE: Eilat, Istanbul and Velenje.
22.05.2023	ALL	<p>In-person consortium meeting in Bonn with Clarity, PARadISE and Buyers Group</p> <p>Clarity arrives without any preparation of subcontractors. Instead Clarity lists many demands to amend the Renovation Package since the originally foreseen costs in the Renovation Package were lower than the costs to be expected only several weeks later.</p>
23.05.2023	Clarity	Clarity sends one (English) RFT-e-mail in copy to Nuremberg's POC for information. Other communication is shared with Nuremberg after explicit request. Knowing exactly what is needed by CLARITY is considered essential to facilitate competent communication with the installers. CLARITY did not implement a German-speaking contact person and continued to communicate in English.
29.05.2023	Clarity	Clarity (SENER) communicated via an automated e-mail the future changes given the internal reorganisation, including the emergence of a spin-off company to separate the infrastructure and Transport Business activities from the Energy Business ones.
30.05.2023	Clarity	In a subsequent email from Clarity responding a request for clarification made by the Lead Procurer on the automated email (dated 29.05.2023) by SENER, it was informed that this change would imply that one of the spin-off companies would sign the contract for Phase III.
01.06.2023	Nuremberg	Nuremberg's POC communicates the first on-site meetings with potential suppliers in first half of June, but an on-site visit by CLARITY is only considered with all potential installers on one day, which is not feasible at short notice, considering the workload of the installation companies.

Date (DD.MM.YYYY)	Sender	Description
07.06.2023	KSENA, EMPIRICA, Clarity	Call to discuss further timing. Demand to sign Specific Contract by 14 June 2023 since the majority of costs have been sourced and all risk for Clarity being known. Clarity anticipated signature by the end of the month.
13.06.2023	Nuremberg	Clarity suggests an on-site meeting with all potential installation companies on 20.06.23, which Nuremberg's POC rejects due to availability of the companies at this short notice and the lack of a full set of offers. CLARITY agrees.
15.06.2023	Nuremberg	Nuremberg's POC urgently requests further details of the dimensioning of the heat pump, to enable the installation company to make an offer. CLARITY only replies with a copy of the technical datasheet of the heat pump.
16.06.2023	AMB	E-mail from Barcelona documenting CLARITY's proposal to split the construction permit (in Spain) in three, one per each provider (PV, HVAC and BMS). This was disregarded due to efficiency reasons and non-compliance with the requests of the Challenge Brief (TD2). Additionally, this request would imply an overburden for the local administration when assessing the requests and would involve many other actors (subcontractors), causing likely delays.
19.06.2023	Clarity	Clarity holds a meeting with the potential installation company for the PV and the BESS. This is the only known direct communication between CLARITY and a potential supplier.
29.06.2023	KSENA (Lead Procurement)	E-mail from Lead Procurer on the status of subcontractors' offers and the compliance with consortium's financial offer, as well as the request to proceed with the necessary steps for ensuring specific contract signature (attached to e-mail). The communication included the deadline for contract signature: 06.07.2023.
05.07.2023	Clarity	Response by Clarity to Lead procurer (dated 29.06.2023) and request for additional time for finalising the process of the specific contract signature.
05.07.2023	EMPIRICA	Follow-up e-mail clarifying further doubts from Clarity (discussed in bilateral meeting). The responses delved into the testing duration for pilot sites, lack of obligation for specific energy savings, management of the invoices and flexibility to find other subcontractors.
21.06.2023	KSENA, EMPIRICA, Clarity	Call to discuss further timing. Demand to sign Specific Contract by end of June 2023 since the majority of costs have been

Date (DD.MM.YYYY)	Sender	Description
		sourced and all risk for CLARITY being known. CLARITY rejects signatures and requests additional funding from pilot sites.
28.06.2023	KSSENA, EMPIRICA, Clarity	Call to discuss further timing. Demand to sign Specific Contract by end of June 2023 since the majority of costs have been sourced and all risk for Clarity being known. This has been prepared as table for discussion. Discovery of cost items in Clarity offer which are unknowingly related to respira
28.06.2023	Clarity	CLARITY delegating translation tasks and subcontractor interaction to Nuremberg.
04.07.2023	KSSENA, EMPIRICA, Clarity	Joined call, procuRE demands to prepare signature of contract by mid-July.
07.07.2023	EMPIRICA	E-mail offering further reassurance about the process to come and its relevance as a milestone for piloting RES solutions in Europe. Repeated offer that a procuRE’s representative (KSSENA and empirica) could travel to Bilbao at short notice to explain the key aspects of the project and why this was strategic in the context of the European energy market. This was rejected in multiple instances arguing the board would not be available for such meeting.
11.07.2023	procuRE	Consortium Meeting: Exchange on continuous non-performance of Clarity. Agreement that situation has not improved. Agreement to assess overall situation. Agreement to request all information on offers not yet shared (contrary to Challenge Brief and Offer description of Co-Design procedure) to perform this task.
12.07.2023	Clarity	Call of Clarity to EMPIRICA referring to 7.7.23 as being "basically right". Stating that removing respirca appears to be the "only option" to ensure Renovation Packages .
12.07.2023	Clarity	<p>E-mail from Clarity asking the Buyers Group to exclude ‘RESPIRA’ (the Artificial Intelligence System to control HVAC), which was originally included in consortium’s proposal for Phase III. A series of additional requirements (per pilot site) altering the solution’s scope were communicated and asked. These included:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AMB: townhall representatives to take care of construction license (POMO) for the changes to the building (not supplier). Also, Clarity asked to avoid requests for design changes from procurer.

Date (DD.MM.YYYY)	Sender	Description
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Nuremberg: more subcontractors' bids (and contacts) to be submitted to Clarity as the previous were deemed too expensive for the supplier's experience with European markets. Additionally, Clarity asked the procurer to take over costs for the cable from the electrical connection to the PV system. GAIA: to take over the costs for the firefighting system, fireproofing insulation and HVAC system for the battery room; or to accept alternative approaches to accommodate the costs of this request by procurer (originally not offered in the renovation package for the site). <p>The above mentioned elements were presented as a pre-requisite to proceed with the contract's signature for Phase III.</p>
14.07.2023	AMB	E-mail from Barcelona representative asking for status of the subcontractors offers and clarification on technical aspects of the offers.
14.07.2023	Clarity	Response by Clarity concerning request for clarification asked by Barcelona.
30.07.2023	KSSENA (Lead Procurer)	Notification on the Buyers Group's final decision, which after reviewing the events documented here, resolves to select SEBR (the third-ranked tender) instead of Clarity (the second-ranked tender) to carry out Phase III implementation in the pilot sites: Barcelona, Vila Nova de Gaia and Nuremberg. The decision was communicated to both suppliers' consortia, inviting them to sign the respective specific contracts.
10.08.2023	Clarity	Clarity makes available all data required for further procedure.
18.08.2023	KSSENA	Thank you for service and invitation to Open Pilot Days.

2.3 Abstracts of winning tenders

Abstracts in order of ranking. The abstracts are taken from the PCP Phase 3 deliverable D3.5a provided in the Annex 6.

2.3.1 PARadISE– R2M – T005

PARadISE addresses the challenge of maximising the share of renewables used in existing buildings, while smoothing the integration of necessary system components, optimising the user’s comfort and facilitating O&M. Thus, PARadISE provides a toolkit composed of reliable and modular hardware and software technologies while helping procurers make informed decisions based on a framework that rates technologies performance. BIM is present throughout the whole process as the major enabler for the implementation of a novel retrofitting methodology with the Heat Pump as the main energy transformer and renewables as the main primary producers, interconnected by an open, flexible and scalable SCADA enabling the EMS implementation and the deployment of smart algorithms for optimal operation. In this context, PARadISE supports procurers not only in the design phase, but through the entire retrofitting process, providing a standardized, low intrusive, and modular interface based on BIM. Finally, PARadISE provides procurers with all the necessary tools and education & training activities so that they can manage the solution during the operation phase.

2.3.2 SEBR – Defcon8 – T002

SEBR (Smart Energy Building Renovation) is a Consortium of companies that retrofits existing buildings with PV, batteries, leds, domotics, HVAC, SaaS, etc. to make them self-sustainable, near Zero energy buildings (nZEB)

Each building (school, offices, households, hotels, hospitals, sports centres, shopping malls etc.) is tailored according to its needs, it is not a one size fits all solution.

We provide:

- technical training to facility managers &
- tips to end users to reduce energy & water usage.

Whenever possible, we buy hardware & contract locally to minimise GHG emissions in transportation and provide better aftersales / maintenance backup support. Speaking the same language and knowing local regulations including government grants is also a reason to subcontract locally.

RES can be forecasted with simulation tools, so, the buyers can know beforehand what to expect, KPIs, environmental impact, savings, expected ROI. All scenarios can be simulated with costs to optimise value for money.

2.4 Next steps

Phase III of the PCP began on July 31st, 2023.

Phase III allocated three sites per suppliers’ consortium. PARadISE will work with Eilat, Istanbul and Velenje; and SEBR will work with Barcelona, Nuremberg and Vila Nova de Gaia.

Currently, Suppliers are finalising planning the activities required for Phase III based on the updated Renovation Packages and the feedback from the procurers. In particular, the subcontractors are needed on-site to order and install equipment defined in the Renovation Package.

Annex 1 PowerPoint Call-Off Invitation

The following slides were presented during a meeting of procuRE and all suppliers present.

Figure 1. Excerpt A - Meeting with suppliers for preparation of offer for Phase III

Supplier perspective: to consider for utilising funding

Phase III - Offer

There will only be two suppliers¹

Quality is linked to KPIs which is linked to design which is linked to equipment

Maybe storage has not yet been fully considered?

You need a very good demonstrator

¹ procuRE is unlike other PCPs where ICT has been procured of which you can multiple in parallel. We have physical buildings limited in number.

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Figure 2. Excerpt B - Meeting with suppliers for preparation of offer for Phase III

There will be, most likely, two sets of three sites for which you will bid with 2 financial offers

Phase III - Offer

Ideal per supplier

- ▶ Both Building Types
- ▶ Northern climate represented

For the benefit of learning

Issues to consider

- ▶ Complexity of sites (building, borders etc.)
- ▶ Timing and resources

Map labels: School, Office

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Annex 2 Invitation letter for Phase III

Dear Contractor,

On behalf of the procuRE Buyers Group you are herewith invited to submit an offer for Phase III (deliverable „O2“) of the PCP in a call-off. Please follow the set of instructions and templates provided for this in the attached call-off package. The call-off package consists of:

- Template and instructions for the updated administrative section (CfT TD5)
- Template and instructions for the updated technical offer (CfT TD6)
- Template and instructions for the updated annex to the technical offer (CfT TD6a)
- Template and instructions for the updated financial offer (CfT TD7)
- Additional information contained as appendixes to this file

The **templates include further instructions** for the specific document (see the executive summary sections). Please read the instructions carefully and prepare your offer for Phase III accordingly. Most changes in TD5 and TD6 were recorded with track changes. The No-Markup version always prevails.

Submission deadline

The offer needs to be submitted **by 11th of April 2023 17:00**, 17:00 Ljubljana local time, UTC+2:00.

Submission format

The financial offer is to be provided for two sets (A and B) of three sites each. Set A contains Velenje (School), Eilat (Office) and Istanbul (Office). Set B contains Barcelona (Office), Gaia (School) and Nuremberg (School). The sets are preliminary and subject to change.

Please submit your offer electronically not later than the deadline specified above. Offers submitted after this deadline will be excluded.

Each PDF must be electronically signed or an additional hand-signed copy provided as a scan to be stored and submitted upon request.

An email must be sent with all attachments collected in one zip-file (no size limit) to suppliers@procure-pcp.eu by the deadline specified above. The email must contain **all items** listed below.

Checklist table for submission:

Check	Document title	Format	Page limit	Word searchable	Emailed?	Signed ?
	Technical offer TD6	PDF	100	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Technical offer TD6a	PDF	-	-	Yes	Yes
	Technical offer TD6a	Excel	-	-	Yes	No
	Financial offer check on ceiling	See TD7 new sheet			No	No
	Financial offer TD7 Set A	PDF	-	-	Yes	Yes
	Financial offer TD7 Set B	PDF	-	-	Yes	Yes
	Financial offer TD7 Set B	Excel	-	-	Yes	No
	Financial offer TD7 Set B	Excel	-	-	Yes	No
	Administrative offer TD5*	PDF	no limit	-	Yes	Yes
	If applicable: Administrative offer TD5*	Word	No limit	Yes with Track Changes	Yes	No

* If any additional forms are required (e.g. DoH) please use templates provided with the original tender. If new forms are provided, include each new file also as a separate copy which is electronically signed.

All Phase III offers must indicate their minimum validity period from submission (at least six months; see instructions in the executive summary of the technical offer).

Please note that the procuRE Call for Tenders provisions remain applicable and binding.

The procuRE Buyers Group is happy to be working with you. Please do not hesitate to ask us any questions you may have.

We thank you for being a valuable solution provider to the global challenge of 100% RES renovation of buildings.

Best regards,

Bostjan Krajnc

- on behalf of procuRE Buyers Group

Appendix 1: Phase III Weighted Award Criteria Scorecard.

Please note that the points and weighting of the award criteria change from phase to phase, as stated in the call for tender. Below is the award criteria table for Phase III taken directly from the original call for your convenience:

Weighted award criteria for Phase III	Maximum points	Threshold	Weight
Technical Criterion			50%
T1 - System Integration: Methodology and Process	30	15	
T2 - Degree of achievement of objectives in demonstration buildings	40	25	
T3 - Training & Education of professionals and users	20	15	
T4 - Innovativeness compared to market state-of-the-art	10	5	
Total for technical	100	60	
Commercial Feasibility Criterion			25%
CF1 - Investment, energy service contracting and financing models / Total cost of ownership	60	40	
CF2 - Commercialisation Plan	40	30	
Total for commercial feasibility	100	70	
Project Management Criterion			25%
PM1- Interface to procurers	25	15	
PM2 - Quality and completeness of the work-plan as well as detail of task and result descriptions	40	25	
PM3 - Feasibility of plan and resources to meet the objectives	35	20	
Total for project management	100	60	
Overall total score for tender	100	60	

Appendix 2: Updated PCP Schedule

Date	Activity
Implementation of Phase I	
10.05.2022	Start of Phase I
13.05.2022	Names of winning Phase I contractors and their project abstracts to be sent to EU and published on procuRE PCP project website
11.06.2022	Visit of Phase I contractors to the premises(s) of the procurer(s) to learn about the operational boundary conditions governing the design of targeted solutions
08.07.2022	Deadline for Phase I core milestones / deliverables
26.07.2022	Phase I contractors notified as to whether they have completed this phase satisfactorily and successfully (invoices can be sent)
09.08.2022	Reports and Summary of the results and conclusions achieved by each contractor during the phase sent to EU
09.08.2022	End of Phase I
Second tender procedure (call-off for Phase II)	
21.06.2022	Launch call-off for Phase II (only offers from contractors that successfully completed Phase I are eligible)
30.06.2022	Deadline for submitting questions on Phase II call-off documents
05.07.2022	Deadline for lead procurer to circulate replies to questions to Phase II tenderers
11.07.2022	Deadline for submitting Phase II offers
12.07.2022	Opening of Phase II offers
21.07.2022	Contractors notified of decision on awarding Phase II contracts
21.07.2022 – 10.08.2022	Standstill period
25.07.2022	Contracts sent for signature by tenderers
08.08.2022	Deadline for receipt of signed contracts
10.08.2022	Date of signature by Lead Procurer
22.08.2022	Signed contracts sent to tenderers
Implementation of Phase II	
10.08.2022	Start of Phase II
15.08.2022	Names of winning Phase II contractors and their project abstracts to be sent to EU and published on procuRE PCP project website
09.12.2022	Deadline for Phase II first version milestone(s)/deliverables
11.04.2023	Deadline for Phase II final milestone(s)/ deliverable(s)
20.04.2023	Phase II contractors notified as to whether they have completed this phase satisfactorily and successfully (second invoice on phase can be sent)
09.05.2023	Reports and Summary of the results and conclusions achieved by each contractor during the phase sent to EU
09.05.2023	End of Phase II
Third tender procedure (call-off for Phase III)	
13.03.2023	Launch call-off for Phase III (only offers from contractors that successfully completed Phase II are eligible)

25.03.2023	Deadline for submitting questions on Phase III call-off documents
30.03.2023	Deadline for lead procurer to circulate replies to questions to Phase II tenderers
11.04.2023	Deadline for submitting Phase III offers
12.04.2023	Opening of Phase III offers
30.04.2023	Contractors notified of decision on awarding Phase II contracts
30.04.2023 – 10.05.2023	Standstill period
30.04.2023	Contracts sent for signature by tenderers
09.05.2023	Deadline for receipt of signed contracts
12.05.2023	Date of signature by Lead Procurer
17.05.2023	Signed contracts sent to tenderers
Implementation of Phase III	
09.05.2023	Start of Phase III
12.05.2023	Names of winning Phase III contractors and their project abstracts to be sent to EU and published on procuRE PCP project website
23-24.05.2023	Consortium Meeting with Suppliers and Procurers in Bonn
06.08.2024	Deadline for Phase III final milestone(s)/ deliverable(s) – Likely extension until October
06.08.2024	Final demonstration of products/services developed during Phase III (<i>including to EU representatives</i>)
20.08.2024	Phase III contractors notified as to whether they have completed this phase satisfactorily and successfully (second invoice in phase can be sent)
03.09.2024	Reports and summary of the results and conclusions achieved by each contractor during the PCP sent to EU for publication purposes.
07.09.2024	End of Phase III – Likely extension until November

Note: The timeline for Phase III is indicative pending an extension of the procuRE Grant Agreement which is to be agreed with the European Commission later in the project. As stated in the procuRE Call for Tenders, Buyers Group reserves the right to adjust the schedule.

Appendix 3: Model Specific Contract Phase II

PREAMBLE

This agreement is a Specific Contract executed and performed under the Framework Agreement concluded between the Buyers Group and the Contractor. The provisions of the Framework Agreement form an integral part of this agreement.

Annex 1: Framework Agreement

Annex 2: Contractor's Offer / Tender

TERMS AND CONDITIONS

Article 1 – Subject of the contract

This specific contract defines the specific terms and conditions for the implementation of the PCP procurement of R&D services set out in Article 3 – for PCP Phase II.

Article 2 – Duration

This contract shall come into force as of the date of signature of the last party and shall continue in full force and effect until terminated in accordance with the provisions of the Framework Agreement or until complete discharge of all obligations and at the latest by [date].

The period of execution of the tasks may be extended only with the express written agreement of the parties before the expiration of the period for execution of the tasks.

Article 3 – R&D services to be provided

The Contractor shall provide the R&D services (tasks, deliverables and milestones) set out in the offer for this phase and deliver the Expected Outcomes specified for this phase in the Request for Tender

Article 4 – Price and payment arrangements

The price to be paid by ENERGY AGENCY OF SAVINJSKA, ŠALEŠKA AND KOROŠKA REGION [KSENA] for the R&D services set out in Article 3 shall be EUR [amount in figures and in words].

Required deliverable/ milestone	Amount of payment	Expected date
D3.5a	10% (ten percent) of contractor's Phase III price	Start of Phase
M3.1,	40% (forty percent) of contractor's Phase III price	3 months after the start of Phase
M3.2, M3.3		4 Months after the start of the Phase
D3.1, D3.2		8 months after the start of Phase & two months before end of Phase
D3.3		Updated documentation and on-site testing of systems 3 months after start of the phase for equipped sites (see Section 2.6). Final and complete documentation 2 months before the end of the Phase
M3.4	15% (fifty percent) of contractor's Phase III price	2 month before end of Phase
D3.4		4 Months before end of Phase
D3.5b, D3.6	35% (thirtyfive percent) of contracto's phase III price	End of Phase

Approval of deliverables and invoicing shall proceed as specified in Section 5.5 of the Request for Tender.

Article 5 – Sites to be supplied

The Contractor has to supply the following sites: [sites allocated].]

SIGNATURES

Authorised to sign for the Buyers Group (Full Name, Date, Place, Signature)

Authorised to sign for the Contractor (Full Name, Date, Place, Signature)

Annex 3: Notification emails

Clartiy

Figure 3. E-mail with Revised Notification for Phase III

procuRE: PCP Phase II results - Revision of supplier choice

Natek Niko <Niko.Natek@kssena.velenje.eu>
 To: Gomez de Iturriaga Pina, Carlos Jaime; Benitez Cardona, Maria del Carmen
 Cc: Ochagavia Gómez, Juan; Georg Vogt; **procuRE**

procuRE_T001_Notification on phase III contract award.pdf
 137 KB

Reply
 Reply All
 Forward

 Thu 03/08/2023 15:45

Dear representatives of CLARITY,

With regards to your participation in the procuRE PCP we're hereby notifying you about the decision of the buyers group to award the contract for phase III to an alternate tenderer.

Thank you and best regards,

KSSENA team
 on behalf of the procuRE buyers group

Zavod Energetska agencija za Savinjsko, Šaleško in Koroško
 Energy Agency of Savinjska, Šaleška and Koroška region
 Koroška cesta 37a, 3320 Velenje, Slovenija

T +386 3 8961 520
 E info@kssena.velenje.eu
 W www.kssena.si

PARadISE

Figure 4. Final Specific contract for Phase III

procuRE: Phase III - Invitation to sign Specific contract

Natek Niko <Niko.Natek@kssena.velenje.eu>
 To: administracion@r2msolution.com
 Cc: Jesús Febres; luisa.candido@prosume.io; **procuRE**

T005_procuRE_Specific contract_Phase III - PARadISE.pdf
 175 KB

Reply
 Reply All
 Forward

 Sun 30/07/2023 10:32

Dear PARadISE,

We invite you to sign the Specific contract for Phase III of the procuRE PCP.

The same administrative process for signing as for the previous phases applies, which I indicate again for your reference. We request that you initial each page of each copy of the contract, sign and date the last page and ensure that two originally signed copies of each contract are sent to our address below. Before sending out the physical copies of the documents, we also kindly ask that you provide us with the scans of the documents via email. We will use this as confirmation in order to begin the formal processes related to phase III implementation immediately.

The formal start of Phase III is the **31st of July 2023**.

We kindly request that you carry out the steps for signing the contract and send out the documents via a trusted courier service tomorrow, so we may ensure a timely commencement of phase III activities.

Thank you very much for your compliance.

Best regards,

KSSENA team
 on behalf of the procuRE buyers group

Documents to be sent to:

Niko Natek / Boštjan Krajnc
 Energy Agency of Savinjska, Šaleška and Koroška Region,
 Koroška cesta 37A,
 3320 Velenje, Slovenia

Zavod Energetska agencija za Savinjsko, Šaleško in Koroško
 Energy Agency of Savinjska, Šaleška and Koroška region
 Koroška cesta 37a, 3320 Velenje, Slovenija

T +386 3 8961 520
 E info@kssena.velenje.eu
 W www.kssena.si

Figure 5. Outcome letter for Phase III

procuRE: PCP Phase II results - Outcome Letter

Natek Niko <Niko.Natek@kssena.veleyenje.eu>
To: administracion@r2msolution.com
Cc: Jesús Febres; luisa.candido@prosume.io; **procuRE**

Reply Reply All Forward [Share icon] [More icon]
Thu 18/05/2023 14:52

Dear PARADISE,

With regards to your participation in phase 2 of the procuRE PCP we're hereby providing the official outcome letter which you may find attached. We will soon also provide you with additional feedback regarding proposed improvements of your solution from the side of the buyers group.

Thank you and best regards,

KSSENA team
on behalf of the procuRE buyers group

Zavod Energetska agencija za Savinjsko, Šaleško in Koroško
Energy Agency of Savinjska, Šaleška and Koroška region
Koroška cesta 37a, 3320 Velenje, Slovenija

T +386 3 8961 520
E info@kssena.veleyenje.eu
W www.kssena.si

Annex 4: Outcome letters

Notification letter T002

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement No. 963648.

Defcon8
Avda Corts Cat 5-7
08173 St. Cugat,
Barcelona, Spain

Velenje, 27th of July 2023

Results of the evaluation of the procuRE Call-off for Phase III

Dear Tenderer,

We are pleased to inform you that your tender has been successful in the above procurement procedure. Your consortium was chosen to supply Barcelona, Vila Nova de Gaia and Nuremberg.

This letter informing you of the award of the contract does not constitute a commitment on the part of the contracting authority. Until signature of the contract by both parties, the contracting authority may cancel the procurement procedure without this entitling you to any compensation. The validity period from submission remains in place.

You will soon receive the Specific Contract for Phase III for your signature.

Should it not be possible to conclude the contract as foreseen, we reserve the right to review our decision and to award the contract to another tenderer, to cancel or abandon the procedure.

We would like to thank you for your participation in this procurement procedure.

Yours faithfully,

Boštjan Krajnc
Director
KSENA

Notification letter T005

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement No. 963648.

R2M Solution Spain SL
Calle Villablanca 85,
28032 Madrid
Spain

Velenje, 17th of May 2023

Results of the evaluation of the procuRE Call-off for Phase III

Dear Tenderer,

We are pleased to inform you that your tender has been successful in the above procurement procedure. Your consortium was chosen to supply Velenje, Eilat and Istanbul.

This letter informing you of the award of the contract does not constitute a commitment on the part of the contracting authority. Until signature of the contract by both parties, the contracting authority may cancel the procurement procedure without this entitling you to any compensation. The validity period from submission remains in place.

You will soon receive the Specific Contract for Phase III for your signature.

Should it not be possible to conclude the contract as foreseen, we reserve the right to review our decision and to award the contract to another tenderer, to cancel or abandon the procedure.

We would like to thank you for your participation in this procurement procedure.

Yours faithfully,

Boštjan Krajnc
Director
KSSENA

Annex 5: Exchange with Clarity on concerning change of supplier

procuRE: Notification to Clarity

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement No. 963648.

SENER INGENIERÍA Y SISTEMAS S.A
AV. ZUGAZARTE, 56.
POSTAL CODE: 48930
GETXO (BIZKAIA, SPAIN)

Velenje, 31st of July 2023

Decision on the award of contract for Phase III (procuRE PCP)

Dear Tenderer,

We hereby inform you that - in line with the provision of this notification letter - we reviewed our decision and award the contract to another tenderer as it is not possible to conclude the contract for Phase III of the procuRE PCP as foreseen.

CLARITY has announced that it sees itself unable or unwilling to deliver a critical component of its offer and wishes to negotiate the terms despite renegotiations being excluded by the request for tender. CLARITY appears to have taken no preparations of the respira system during Phase I and Phase II to make it suitable and a commercially viable solution for public buildings such as schools and offices with the lack of progress only becoming apparent to the Buyers Group in recent weeks. The Buyers Group must conclude that CLARITY shows no prospect of deploying a commercially viable and sufficiently innovative solution which can be replicated in other buildings.

CLARITY has failed to provide the services tendered through the Challenge Brief including a turn-key ready solution following a one-face-to-the-customer approach for which funding has been received during Phase I and II. CLARITY has failed to implement or foresee requests made by procurers and/or required by law at site, source realistic local prices at sites, include all required equipment and services and subcontractors needed for lawful implementation during Phase II for a period of three months since the results of the Phase III have been announced. The resulting (minor) deviation is put forward to be covered by the procurers instead of reallocating such budget. The failure and delay occurred despite accommodating the contractors wish for support in sourcing subcontractors and significant effort invested by the allocated procurers to identify, source, contact and negotiate with subcontractors. Recently, further need of such activity has been announced which would cause further unspecified delays.

Overall, CLARITY appears to have a calculating view on what it is willing and ready to deliver within this pre-commercial research and development project including components and services constituting the CLARITY proposition and the procuRE Challenge Brief (i.e. high-RES shares, active control, re-imagining of planning and implementation procedures, reducing effort for procurers). Upon initialisation of Phase III, CLAIRITY conditionally requested a revisit of the site allocation. Although there was no need for procurers to respond, procures have accommodated this first request (causing extensive inner tension) in the

understanding that this was the central reason for internal procedures to halt the signature of the Specific Contract which turned out to be not correct.

The combination of above - scope shifting, delays, and unwillingness to accommodate research partners - puts into question whether CLARITY has any intent to commercialise any solution as a viable offer for municipalities operating schools and offices and whether it feels obliged by the principles of research integrity. Rather than innovating on the procedures in construction, CLARITY defends the status quo counter to the research objective.

We take note that a good share of the observations made have not been directly caused by the team delivering the project (i.e. Juan Ochagavía Gómez and his team) but decisions at executive level at SENER. We understand SENER's board and by extension the risk department appears to have changed focused since signature of the Framework Agreement and no longer supports R&D projects with the focus of procuRE and/or PCPs in principle. We consider this change regrettable but cannot longer tolerate that the inner proceeding at SENER delays the work and undermines the intent of the entire procuRE project.

In order to allow the procurers to mitigate the situation and proceed with the project:

- Please submit **all commercial offers and technical documentation** surrounding the offers and sites received and processed at Barcelona, Gaia and Nuremberg immediately since it constitutes foreground generated by the project. The information can be provided as an archive.
- Please release the confidentiality on Renovation Packages for Gaia, Barcelona and Nuremberg (D2.2.) as a whole or as an edited version (excluding confidential elements) in accordance with Article 7 **within one week**.

In accordance with Article 17(1), the EU may hold the Contractor liable for damages sustained as a result of failing to implement the Framework Agreement properly in case of which compensation must be paid. This current step is without prejudice to any rights, remedies or obligations of the Contractor.

In accordance with Article 18, the obligations of the Framework Agreement remain in force.

We thank the CLARITY team for the insights gathered through the DAE tool development of which progressed through the funding received from procuRE and look forward for the solution to be franchised or provided to planners in the private and public sector.

At this moment, the procuRE project - the procurers of Vinska Gora – Velenje, Barcelona, Istanbul, Nuremberg, Vila Nova de Gaia – Porto and Eilat and their partners - intent to move on and implement the sites as promised to its Contracting Authority, the European Commission. We hope the swift exchange of information will help us facilitate this objective and procuRE is able to document the outcome of the Phase III call-off without need for major documentation and effort.

Yours faithfully,

Boštjan Krajnc

Director

KSSENA

CLARITY: Response to procuRE

ENERGY AGENCY OF SAVINJSKA, ŠALEŠKA AND KOROŠKA REGION (KSEENA)

KOROŠKA CESTA 37A
3320 VELENJE
SLOVENIA

Attn: Boštjan Kranjnc
Niko Natek

Re: Communication from KSEENA sent by email on August 3, 2023 – Decision on the award of contract for Phase III (ProcuRE PCP).

Madrid, August 10, 2023

Dear Sirs,

Reference is made to communication sent by KSEENA to SENER INGENIERÍA Y SISTEMAS S.A. (the Contractor) on August 3, 2023, regarding the decision on the award of contract of Phase III for ProcuRE PCP.

Please mind that SENER has never stated its inability or unwillingness to deliver any component that was part of its original proposal, nor has it failed to fulfill its obligations under the Framework Agreement.

However, what has taken place over the last three months, with KSEENA's knowledge, has been certain unofficial discussions, held whether by email and over the phone, and as result of that, SENER provided an alternative solution to the provided proposal, in no way to be considered as imposed, determined or final, to which we received no response other than the aforementioned communication.

SENER'S support for R&D projects cannot be questioned, nor can be its commitment with ProcuRE project.

In this sense and based on the foregoing, please be assured that SENER's total commitment is to meet its obligations assumed in its submitted proposal, open in any case and willing to collaborate with any alternative solution KSEENA may suggest, to be assessed and considered by SENER, as long as it does not incur additional liability.

As a way of offering evidence of good will, please see below the link to the requested information (located in files of ProcuRE Clarity Teams Group):

[ProcuRE "Clarity" - Documentation requested by Lead Procurer 03-08-2023 - Todos los documentos \(sharepoint.com\):](#)

<https://sener365.sharepoint.com/sites/ProcuREClarity/Documentos%20compartidos/Forms/AllItems.aspx?csf=1&web=1&e=f4Eg4d&cid=d099123f%2D732f%2D442d%2D8a47%2Df83d35de53b9&RootFolder=%2Fsites%2FProcuREClarity%2FDocumentos%20compartidos%2FGeneral%2FPublished%2F03%5FPhase%203%2FDocumentation%20requested%20by%20Lead%20Procurer%5F03%2D08%2D2023&FolderCTID=0x01200068C6726A1A1AAF49A1A2505A2610C8A2>

We therefore understand that having KSENA accepted the Contractor's initial offer and having SENER confirmed that it will be provided without any subsequent alteration, we would be in a position to sign the contract for phase III of the ProcuRE project.

We remain at your disposal to further discuss or clarify any consideration you may have in this regard.

Yours faithfully,

16573293E
ENRIQUE
RUBEN
GOMEZ (R:
A10770345)

Digitally signed by 16573293E ENRIQUE RUBEN GOMEZ (R: A10770345)
DN: Description=Ref:AEAT/AEAT0030/PUESTO 1/92002/15062023092100, SERIALNUMBER= IDCES-16573293E, O=ENRIQUE RUBEN, SN= GOMEZ CRISTOBAL, CN=16573293E ENRIQUE RUBEN GOMEZ (R: A10770345), OID.2.5.4.97= VATES=A10770345, O=SENER MOBILITY SOCIEDAD ANONIMA, C=ES
Reason: I am approving this document with my legally binding signature
Location:
Date: 2023.08.10 16:26:49+0200
Foxit PDF Reader Version: 12.1.2

Enrique Rubén Gómez Cristóbal
Legal Authorised Representative

procuRE: Invitation to Clarity to join Open Pilot Days

Info KSSENA <info@kssena.velenje.eu>

To: enrique.gomez@sener.es

Cc: Ochagavía Gómez, Juan

Fri 18.8.23 12:53

Nekateri ljudje, ki so prejeli to sporočilo, ne dobijo pogosto e-pošte od osebe info@kssena.velenje.eu. [Več informacij o tem, zakaj je to pomembno.](#)

Dear Mr. Gómez Cristóbal,

In light of the recent flooding across Slovenia, please excuse the slow response. We thank you for preparing and releasing the project related information swiftly!

We wish to inform you that the project has been awarded and the specific contracts were signed by both suppliers and the lead procurer. Implementation thereof has started in order to fulfil the deadlines of the procuRE project.

We hope that the R&D funding received in Phases 1 and 2 had advanced SENER's ESCO-efforts and renovation solutions for 100% renewable energy supply of public buildings. Being completed, we would welcome if the funding for new components of DEA have aided the commercialization of such a product towards individual municipal buildings.

We thank you for your interest, contributions and effort in our joint mission on the energy transition. We aim to share these with the wider public. We hereby also invite you to join one of our open pilot days towards the end of the project.

Best regards,

Boštjan Krajnc, KSSENA
on behalf of the procuRE buyers group

Zavod Energetska agencija za Savinjsko, Šaleško in Koroško
Energy Agency of Savinjska, Šaleška and Koroška region
Koroška cesta 37a, 3320 Velenje, Slovenija

T +386 3 8961 520
E info@kssena.velenje.eu
W www.kssena.si

From: Gomez Cristobal, Enrique Ruben <enrique.gomez@sener.es>
Sent: Thursday, August 10, 2023 4:33 PM
To: Natek Niko <Niko.Natek@kssena.velenje.eu>
Cc: Georg Vogt <georg.vogt@empirica.com>; procuRE@empirica.com; Ochagavía Gómez, Juan <juan.ochagavia@sener.es>
Subject: RE: procuRE: PCP Phase II results - Revision of supplier choice

Dear Sirs,

Annex 6: Contractor details and Project abstracts

SEBR – Defcon8 – T002

Contractor Details	Type/ size of legal entity	Place of performance of contract activities	Logo
<p><u>Main contractor</u></p> <p>Defcon8 Avda Corts Catalanes 5 08173 St.Cugat, Barcelona, Spain Name Javier Ray Phone +34 620988517 E-mail jray@defcon8.com</p>	SME	<p>% of contract value allocated to main contractor:116.000 [15,47] %</p> <p>% of activities for the contract performed by the main contractor in EU Member States or countries associated with Horizon 2020: [100] %</p>	
<p>Name ITEC Address C/Wellington 19 08018 Barcelona Name Licinio Alfaro Phone +93 3093404 E-mail lalfaro@itec.cat</p>	Non profit institute	<p>% of contract value allocated to contractor [290.000]: [38,67] %</p> <p>% of activities for the contract performed by ITEC in EU Member States or countries associated with Horizon 2020: [100] %</p>	
<p>Name Mondas Address Emmy Noether Str2 79110 Freiburg Name Volkmar Boerner Phone +49(0)761216089-20 Volkmar.Boerner@mondas-gmbh.de</p>	SME	<p>% of contract value allocated to contractor [210.000]: [28] %</p> <p>% of activities for the contract performed by Mondas in EU Member States or countries associated with Horizon 2020: [100] %</p>	
<p>Name CIFE Address 81 rue de France 06000 Nice, FR Name Rachel Guyet Phone +33493979397 Rachel.Guyet@CIFE.eu</p>	SME	<p>% of contract value allocated to contractor [24.000]: [3,2] %</p> <p>% of activities for the contract performed by CIFE in EU Member States or countries associated with Horizon 2020: [100] %</p>	
<p>Name 3OC Address -rue des Halles 15 75001 Paris Name Chloe Chavardes Phone +33661124367 chloe@threeoclock.co</p>	SME	<p>% of contract value allocated to contractor [59.000]: [7,87] %</p> <p>% of activities for the contract performed by CIFE in EU Member States or countries associated with Horizon 2020: [100] %</p>	

Name Lancey Energy Storage Address 37 rue Diderot 38000 Grenoble, France Name Raphael Meyer Phone +33.4.58.00.36.96 E-mail r.meyer@lancey.fr	SME	% of contract value allocated to contractor [20.000]: [2,67] % % of activities for the contract performed by Lancey in EU Member States or countries associated with Horizon 2020: [100] %	
SUBCONTRACTOR Name Edison Electronics Address C/Xarol 4A Name Angel Martinez Phone +34 93 4655204 a.martinezbarbera@edisone.com	SME	% of contract value allocated to contractor [31.000]: [4,13] % % of activities for the contract performed by Edison in EU Member States or countries associated with Horizon 2020: [100] %	

Project abstract (+/- 1000 characters maximum)

SEBR (Smart Energy Building Renovation) is a Consortium of companies that retrofits existing buildings with PV, batteries, leds, domotics, HVAC, SaaS,etc, to make them self-sustainable, near Zero energy buildings (nZEB)

Each building (school, offices, households, hotels, hospitals, sports centres, shopping malls etc.) is tailored according to it's needs, it's not a one size fits all solution.

We provide :

- technical training to facility managers &
- tips to end users to reduce energy & water usage.

Whenever possible, we buy hardware & contract locally to minimise GHG emissions in transportation and provide better aftersales / maintenance backup support. Speaking the same language and knowing local regulations including government grants is also a reason to subcontract locally.

RES can be forecasted with simulation tools, so, the buyers can know beforehand what to expect, KPIs, environmental impact, savings, expected ROI. All scenarios can be simulated with costs to optimise value for money.

Previous EU funding

Is the project based on / a continuation of R&D activities that were previously funded by the EU?: No

PARidSE– R2M – T005

Contactor Details	Type/ size of legal entity	Place of performance of contract activities	Logo
R2M Solution Spain SL (Main contractor) Avenida de Manoteras 24, Planta 2, 28050, Madrid Jesús Febres +34 650 83 56 17 paradise@r2msolution.com	SME	% of contract value allocated to main contractor: 44% % of activities for the contract performed by the main contractor in EU Member States or countries associated with Horizon 2020: 100 %	
R2M Solution SRL Via Fratelli Cuzio, 42, Pavia, 27100 Lorenzo Cifariello +39 0382 1726596 procure@r2msolution.com	SME	% of contract value allocated to main contractor: 4% % of activities for the contract performed by the main contractor in EU Member States or countries associated with Horizon 2020: 100 %	
Prosume SRL Corso Venezia 54, Milan, 20124 Alessia Borge +34 686 74 60 74 alessia@prosume.io	SME	% of contract value allocated to main contractor: 0% % of activities for the contract performed by the main contractor in EU Member States or countries associated with Horizon 2020: 100 %	
ENDEF Engineering SL Calle P-A, 11, Ciudad de Transporte, Zaragoza, 50008 Yolanda Lara +34 976 36 58 11 yolanda.lara@endef.com	SME	% of contract value allocated to main contractor: 40% % of activities for the contract performed by the main contractor in EU Member States or countries associated with Horizon 2020: 100 %	
Aire Limpio 2000 S.L. Plaza de la Castellana 143, Planta 11, 28046 Madrid Vicente Pinto Madrid +34 914170428 vpinto@airelimpio.com	SME	% of contract value allocated to main contractor: 12% % of activities for the contract performed by the main contractor in EU Member States or countries associated with Horizon 2020: 100 %	

Project abstract (+/- 1000 characters maximum)

Project funded by the EU Horizon 2020 Programme

PARadISE addresses the challenge of maximising the share of renewables used in existing buildings, while smoothing the integration of necessary system components, optimising the user's comfort and facilitating O&M. Thus, PARadISE provides a toolkit composed of reliable and modular hardware and software technologies while helping procurers make informed decisions based on a framework that rates technologies performance. BIM is present throughout the whole process as the major enabler for the implementation of a novel retrofitting methodology with the Heat Pump as the main energy transformer and renewables as the main primary producers, interconnected by an open, flexible and scalable SCADA enabling the EMS implementation and the deployment of smart algorithms for optimal operation. In this context, PARadISE supports procurers not only in the design phase, but through the entire retrofitting process, providing a standardized, low intrusive, and modular interface based on BIM. Finally, PARadISE provides procurers with all the necessary tools and education & training activities so that they can manage the solution during the operation phase.

Previous EU funding

Is the project based on / a continuation of R&D activities that were previously funded by the EU?:
YES

If yes, identify this EU funding:

- [H2020 - NGI] - [LEDGER] - [825268]: Prosume - Data structure and protocol
- [H2020] - [LOWUP] - [723930]: Endef - Unglazed PVT
- [H2020] - [MINISTOR] - [869821]: Endef - First PVT with half-cells
- [H2020] - [HESTIA] - [957823]: R2M ES - Building modelling & MPC

Annex 7: TED Contract Award Notice

<https://ted.europa.eu/udl?uri=TED:NOTICE:564280-2023:TEXT:EN:HTML>

Slovenia–Velenje: Research and experimental development services

2023/S 180–564280

Contract award notice

Results of the procurement procedure

Services

Legal Basis:

Directive 2014/24/EU

Section I: Contracting authority

I.1) Name and addresses

Official name: Energy agency of Savinjska, Šaleška and Koroška region (KSSENA)

National registration number: SI58743359

Postal address: Koroška cesta 37A

Town: Velenje

NUTS code: SI034 Savinjska

Postal code: 3320

Country: Slovenia

Contact person: Niko Natek

E-mail: suppliers@procure-pcp.eu

Telephone: +386 38961/520

Internet address(es):

Main address: www.kssena.si/en

Address of the buyer profile: www.procure-pcp.eu

I.1) Name and addresses

Official name: Àrea Metropolitana de Barcelona

National registration number: ESP0800258F

Postal address: c/62 num. 16–18, ed. B 6a planta, Zona Tranca

Town: Barcelona

NUTS code: ES511 Barcelona

Postal code: 08040

Country: Spain

Contact person: Gil Llado

E-mail: suppliers@procure-pcp.eu

Telephone: +34 932/235/151

Fax: +34 932/234/790

Internet address(es):

Main address: www.amb.cat/en/home

Address of the buyer profile: www.procure-pcp.eu

I.1)Name and addresses

Official name: Stadt Nürnberg – Hochbauamt, Kommunales Energiemanagement und Bauphysik

National registration number: DE133552578

Postal address: ZA-KEM, Marientorgraben 11

Town: Nürnberg

NUTS code: DE254 Nürnberg, Kreisfreie Stadt

Postal code: 90402

Country: Germany

Contact person: Alexander Nordhus

E-mail: suppliers@procure-pcp.eu

Telephone: +49 911/231/14584

Fax: +49 911/231/7630

Internet address(es):

Main address: www.nuernberg.de/internet/stadtportal_e

Address of the buyer profile: www.procure-pcp.eu

I.1)Name and addresses

Official name: Energaia – Energy Agency South of the Porto Metropolitan Area

National registration number: PT504454536

Postal address: Av. Manuel Violas, 476, Sala 23

Town: Vila Nova de Gaia

NUTS code: PT11A Área Metropolitana do Porto

Postal code: 4410-137

Country: Portugal

Contact person: Luís Filipe Caeiro Castanheira

E-mail: suppliers@procure-pcp.eu

Telephone: +351 22/374/72/50

Internet address(es):

Main address: www.energaia.pt/en

Address of the buyer profile: www.procure-pcp.eu

I.1)Name and addresses

Official name: Municipality of Eilat

National registration number: IL500226006

Postal address: HATIVAT HANEDEV PO Box – 14

Town: Eilat

NUTS code: IL Israel

Postal code: 88100

Country: Israel

Contact person: Assaf Admon

E-mail: suppliers@procure-pcp.eu

Telephone: +972 8/6367111

Internet address(es):

Main address: www.eilat.city/en/municipality-of

Address of the buyer profile: www.procure-pcp.eu

I.1) Name and addresses

Official name: Istanbul Metropolitan Municipality

National registration number: TR4810024824

Postal address: Osmaniye Mahallesi Cobancesme Kosuyolu Bulvari No 5 Bakirköy

Town: Istanbul

NUTS code: TR10 İstanbul

Postal code: 34568

Country: Turkey

Contact person: Ülkü Gül

E-mail: suppliers@procure-pcp.eu

Telephone: +90 2123126363/666044

Internet address(es):

Main address: www.ibb.istanbul/en

Address of the buyer profile: www.procure-pcp.eu

I.2) Information about joint procurement

The contract involves joint procurement

In the case of joint procurement involving different countries, state applicable national procurement law:

This pre-commercial procurement is carried out by KSENA who was appointed as lead procurer in the name and on behalf of the buyers group listed in I.1. The applicable national law is Slovenian.

The contract is awarded by a central purchasing body

I.4) Type of the contracting authority

Regional or local agency/office

I.5) Main activity

Other activity: Energy

Section II: Object

II.1) Scope of the procurement

II.1.1) Title:

Pre-commercial Procurement (PCP) to buy R&D (research and development) services for Breakthrough Solutions for 100% Renewable Energy Supply in Buildings

II.1.2) Main CPV code

73100000 Research and experimental development services

II.1.3) Type of contract

Services

II.1.4) Short description:

procuRE is a PCP to buy R&D services to support cities' transition to carbon neutrality. The procurement aims to trigger new solutions to be developed and tested to address the common challenge: Achieving 100% Renewable Energy Supply in existing public buildings.

Suppliers are to design, develop, and test an innovative Renovation Approach capable of generating Renovation Packages delivering 100% renewable energy supply to any existing non-residential building with adequate envelope quality. The Renovation Approach is to be tested through generating and implementing Renovation Packages for specific non-residential buildings in Buyers Group portfolios, the Demonstration Sites.

More information can be found on the procuRE website: <https://procure-pcp.eu>.

II.1.6) Information about lots

This contract is divided into lots: no

II.1.7) Total value of the procurement (excluding VAT)

Value excluding VAT: 4 147 489.00 EUR

II.2) Description

II.2.2) Additional CPV code(s)

09300000 Electricity, heating, solar and nuclear energy

09310000 Electricity

09330000 Solar energy

09331000 Solar panels

09331100 Solar collectors for heat production

09331200 Solar photovoltaic modules

09332000 Solar installation

31121300 Wind-energy generators

31158100 Battery chargers

31161900 Voltage-control systems

31162000 Parts of transformers, inductors and static converters

31162100 Parts of condensers

31174000 Power supply transformers

31200000 Electricity distribution and control apparatus

31210000 Electrical apparatus for switching or protecting electrical circuits

31400000 Accumulators, primary cells and primary batteries

31440000 Batteries

31682000 Electricity supplies

32441100 Telemetry surveillance system

35125100 Sensors

38128000 Meteorology instrument accessories

38433200 Emission measurement equipment

38551000 Energy meters

39715000 Water heaters and heating for buildings; plumbing equipment

39715100 Electric instantaneous or storage water heaters and immersion heaters

39715200 Heating equipment

39715210 Central-heating equipment

39715220 Electric heating resistors

39715230 Electric soil-heating apparatus

39715240 Electric space-heating apparatus

39717200 Air-conditioning appliances

42510000 Heat-exchange units, air-conditioning and refrigerating equipment, and filtering machinery

44110000 Construction materials

44111000 Building materials

44112000 Miscellaneous building structures

44115000 Building fittings

44115800 Building internal fittings

45310000 Electrical installation work

48000000 Software package and information systems

48211000 Platform interconnectivity software package

48600000 Database and operating software package

48610000 Database systems

48611000 Database software package

48612000 Database-management system

48613000 Electronic data management (EDM)

65400000 Other sources of energy supplies and distribution

71314000 Energy and related services

71314200 Energy-management services

71314300 Energy–efficiency consultancy services
 71314310 Heating engineering services for buildings
 71321000 Engineering design services for mechanical and electrical installations for buildings
 71321100 Construction economics services
 71321200 Heating–system design services
 71323100 Electrical power systems design services
 71334000 Mechanical and electrical engineering services
 72212190 Educational software development services
 72212211 Platform interconnectivity software development services
 72212931 Training software development services
 72222300 Information technology services
 80420000 E–learning services
 71333000 Mechanical engineering services

II.2.3)Place of performance

NUTS code: DE254 Nürnberg, Kreisfreie Stadt

NUTS code: ES511 Barcelona

NUTS code: IL Israel

NUTS code: PT11A Área Metropolitana do Porto

NUTS code: SI034 Savinjska

NUTS code: TR10 İstanbul

Main site or place of performance:

Testing is expected to take place in Velenje (Slovenia); Barcelona (Spain); Nuremberg (Germany); Vila Nova de Gaia (Portugal); Istanbul (Turkey); Eilat (Israel).

II.2.4)Description of the procurement:

The procurement will take the form of a pre–commercial procurement (PCP) under which R&D service contracts will be awarded to R&D providers in parallel in a phased approach. This will make it possible to compare competing alternative solutions. Each selected operator will be awarded a framework agreement that covers three R&D phases. The three phases are: solution design, prototype development, original development and validation and testing of a limited volume of first products or services. After each phase, intermediate evaluations will be carried out to select the best of the competing solutions. The contractors with the best value–for–money solutions will be offered a specific contract for the next phase.

The selected operators will retain ownership of the intellectual property rights (IPRs) that they generate during the PCP and will be able to use them to exploit the full market potential of the

developed solutions i.e. beyond the procurement. The market potential is estimated to be the majority of educational buildings (780,000) and offices (3.4 million) across Europe.

In their proposal, tenderers are requested to describe a Renovation Approach which can be applied to any school or office across the EU in response to the Challenge Brief (TD2). The Renovation Approach constitutes the set of methods, technologies, services and devices integrated in a well-documented toolkit with which suppliers tackle the 100% RES challenge in any specific building. During the project, tenderers are expected to apply their Renovation Approach in full to the Demonstration Sites. In their proposal, suppliers are to apply the relevant part of their Renovation Approach on two hypothetical reference buildings and report on the expected resulting performance of those buildings. The proposal is rated according to the Weighted Award Criteria.

In Phase I, six contractors apply their Renovation Approach and develop a specific Renovation Package for each of the six Demonstration Sites. The design level is schematic; planning and calculations are preliminary. Contractors and procurers interact via the Co-Design procedure (such a procedure must be included in the Renovation Approach) to clarify detail and decision-making. This phase aims to verify the conceptual, technological, organisational, regulatory, safety and budgetary feasibility of the solutions.

In Phase II, four contractors refine and increase the level of detail of their designs and organise tests of all user-facing ICT-systems. The design level is as detailed as possible without the requirement to constitute construction drawings. Planning and calculations should be final. The use of the Co-Design procedure should be intensified. This phase aims to turn the schematic design to detailed designs preparing all parties involved for rapid implementation; and to give future users the opportunity to test all ICT-systems.

In Phase III, two contractors implement their Renovation Packages at the three Demonstration Sites allocated to them. Designs are turned into construction drawings, the solutions are installed, made operational, maintained and performance data collected. Contractors and procurers interact via the Continuous Commissioning procedure (this must be included in the Renovation Approach) and demonstrate how O&M and contracting plays out in real-life. This phase serves to verify both the prototype Renovation Packages and the whole prototype Renovation Approach.

After the end of the project, it is the intent of procurers to continue the operation of the solutions at all Demonstrations Sites. To enable this, contractors will submit performance and O&M offers during Phase III based on the Renovation Package submitted. There is the possibility of a follow-up project (PPI) to ensure solutions can be scaled up depending on project success and whether service prices are, at this point, commercially competitive or require further support.

II.2.5) Award criteria

Quality criterion – Name: Quality / Weighting: 80%

Price – Weighting: 20%

II.2.11) Information about options

Options: no

II.2.13) Information about European Union funds

The procurement is related to a project and/or programme financed by European Union funds: yes

Identification of the project:

This procurement receives funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme, under Grant Agreement No 963648– procuRE (<https://procure-pcp.eu>). The EU has given a grant for this procurement but is not participating as a contracting authority in the procurement.

II.2.14)Additional information

procuRE carried out a series of open market consultation (OMC) events in the period 22 April 2021 – 9 July 2021 to inform the specifications of the tender. All materials and recording are available at <https://procure-pcp.eu>. Participation in the OMC events is not a prerequisite for submitting a tender for this call.

Section IV: Procedure

IV.1)Description

IV.1.1)Type of procedure

Open procedure

IV.1.3)Information about a framework agreement or a dynamic purchasing system

The procurement involves the establishment of a framework agreement

IV.1.8)Information about the Government Procurement Agreement (GPA)

The procurement is covered by the Government Procurement Agreement: no

IV.2)Administrative information

IV.2.1)Previous publication concerning this procedure

Notice number in the OJ S: [2021/S 231-609058](#)

IV.2.8)Information about termination of dynamic purchasing system

IV.2.9)Information about termination of call for competition in the form of a prior information notice

Section V: Award of contract

Contract No: T005

Title:

Pre-commercial Procurement (PCP) to buy R&D (research and development) services for Breakthrough Solutions for 100% Renewable Energy Supply in Buildings

A contract/lot is awarded: yes

V.2)Award of contract

V.2.1)Date of conclusion of the contract:

31/07/2023

V.2.2)Information about tenders

Number of tenders received: 3

Number of tenders received from SMEs: 2

Number of tenders received from tenderers from other EU Member States: 0

Number of tenders received from tenderers from non-EU Member States: 0

Number of tenders received by electronic means: 3

The contract has been awarded to a group of economic operators: yes

V.2.3) Name and address of the contractor

Official name: R2M Solution Spain SL

Town: Madrid

NUTS code: ES300 Madrid

Country: Spain

The contractor is an SME: yes

V.2.3) Name and address of the contractor

Official name: R2M Solution SRL

Town: Pavia

NUTS code: ITC48 Pavia

Country: Italy

The contractor is an SME: yes

V.2.3) Name and address of the contractor

Official name: Prosume SRL

Town: Milan

NUTS code: ITC4C Milano

Country: Italy

The contractor is an SME: yes

V.2.3) Name and address of the contractor

Official name: Endef Engineering SL

Town: Zaragoza

NUTS code: ES243 Zaragoza

Country: Spain

The contractor is an SME: yes

V.2.3) Name and address of the contractor

Official name: Aire Limpio 2000 SL

Town: Madrid

NUTS code: ES30 Comunidad de Madrid

Country: Spain

The contractor is an SME: yes

V.2.4) Information on value of the contract/lot (excluding VAT)

Total value of the contract/lot: 4 147 489.00 EUR

V.2.5) Information about subcontracting**Section V: Award of contract****Contract No:** T002**Title:**

SEBR

A contract/lot is awarded: yes

V.2) Award of contract**V.2.1) Date of conclusion of the contract:**

31/07/2023

V.2.2) Information about tenders

Number of tenders received: 3

Number of tenders received from SMEs: 2

Number of tenders received from tenderers from other EU Member States: 0

Number of tenders received from tenderers from non-EU Member States: 0

Number of tenders received by electronic means: 3

The contract has been awarded to a group of economic operators: yes

V.2.3) Name and address of the contractor

Official name: Defcon8 Enterprise

Town: Barcelona

NUTS code: ES511 Barcelona

Country: Spain

The contractor is an SME: yes

V.2.3) Name and address of the contractor

Official name: Lancey Energy Storage

Town: Grenoble

NUTS code: FRK24 Isère

Country: France

The contractor is an SME: yes

V.2.3) Name and address of the contractor

Official name: ITEC

Town: Barcelona

NUTS code: ES511 Barcelona

Country: Spain

The contractor is an SME: no

V.2.3) Name and address of the contractor

Official name: Mondas

Town: Freiburg

NUTS code: DE131 Freiburg im Breisgau, Stadtkreis

Country: Germany

The contractor is an SME: yes

V.2.3) Name and address of the contractor

Official name: CIFE

Town: Nice

NUTS code: FRL03 Alpes-Maritimes

Country: France

The contractor is an SME: yes

V.2.3) Name and address of the contractor

Official name: 3OC

Town: Paris

NUTS code: FR101 Paris

Country: France

The contractor is an SME: yes

V.2.4) Information on value of the contract/lot (excluding VAT)

Total value of the contract/lot: 4 147 489.00 EUR

V.2.5) Information about subcontracting**Section VI: Complementary information****VI.3) Additional information:**

The PCP procurement is exempted from the WTO Government Procurement Agreement (GPA), the EU public procurement directives and the national laws that implement them (because it concerns the procurement of R&D services where the benefits do not accrue exclusively to the contracting authority for its use in the conduct of its own affairs).

VI.4) Procedures for review**VI.4.1) Review body**

Official name: DRŽAVNA REVIZIJSKA KOMISIJA ZA REVIZIJO POSTOPKOV ODDAJE JAVNIH NAROČIL

Postal address: Slovenska cesta 54

Town: Ljubljana

Postal code: 1000

Country: Slovenia

Internet address: <https://portalerevizija.si/>

VI.4.3) Review procedure

Precise information on deadline(s) for review procedures:

Precise information on deadline(s) for review procedures:

Decisions taken with regard to the selection of Suppliers, awarding them with Phases 1, 2 or 3 or excluding them from the procuRE PCP Procedure can be challenged by means of an administrative remedy within a period of 10 days upon the formal notification of the decision. A decision dismissing the appeal could be challenged before the District Court of Velenje. Any dispute or claim arising out of or in connection with the execution of the framework agreement or of the phases contracts entered into between the buyers group and the supplier shall be heard by the District Court of Velenje.

VI.5)Date of dispatch of this notice:

14/09/2023